

EFFECTIVENESS OF COMPETENCY BASED EDUCATION ON KNOWLEDGE AND SKILL REGARDING SELECTED OBSTETRIC COMPLICATIONS AMONG FINAL YEAR B.Sc NURSING STUDENTS IN A SELECTED NURSING COLLEGE AT PUDUCHERRY

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ABSTRACT:

INTRODUCTION: All pregnant women are at risk of developing obstetric & life threatening Complications during pregnancy & delivery. These risks are present in every society and in every setting. At least 40% of all pregnant women will experience obstetric complications during their pregnancies. Aim evaluate the Effectiveness of Competency Based Education on Knowledge and Skill regarding the selected obstetric complications among the final year B.Sc Nursing students.

METHODS: Pre Experimental (One group Pre-test and Post-test) research design was adopted. Totally 80 final year B.Sc Nursing students was selected by purposive sampling technique was used. Pretest was conducted to assess the knowledge on Anemia and Pregnancy Induced Hypertension by using structured knowledge questionnaires, skill regarding administration of magnesium sulphate and iron sucrose, monitoring blood pressure and Fetal Heart Rate by using OSCE checklist. Competency Based Education was given in Selected Obstetric Complications. Post-test was conducted by using same Knowledge questionnaires and Skill by using OSCE Checklist after 1weeks.

RESULTS: The result revealed that the paired 't' test value 82.889 , 89.467 for anemia and Pregnancy Induced Hypertension respectively which shows that it was a statistically significant at $p < 0.001$. In skill, the paired 't' value of 81.993, 85.618, 69.560, 63.145 for administration of MgSo₄ and iron sucrose, Blood Pressure, Fetal Heart Rate respectively. It shows that it was a statistically significant at $p < 0.001$.

CONCLUSION: Competency Based Education was effective in improving the Knowledge and Skill in selected obstetric complications among final year B.Sc Nursing Students.

KEYWORDS: Competency Based Education, Final year B.Sc nursing student, Knowledge and Skill, Obstetric complication.

INTRODUCTION:

Obstetric complications are the pregnancy and childbirth-related morbidity and mortality that occurs during the process of conception till childbirth. Worldwide, every minute of every day, one-woman dies of pregnancy related complications. Nearly 6, 00, 000 women die each year, of these 99 % of death occurs in developing countries. Every single woman 30 % women

develop life long illness and injuries related to pregnancy and childbirth, 15 % of the woman develops life-threatening complications. Most maternal deaths in India are caused by complications such as hemorrhage (29 %), anemia (19 %), hypertensive disorders (8 %) of pregnancy.⁽¹⁾

All pregnant women are at risk of developing obstetric & life threatening Complications during pregnancy & delivery. Pregnancy is not a disease but a normal physiological process, it is associated with certain risks to health and survival of both for the mother and newborn baby. These risks are present in every society and in every setting. At least 40% of all pregnant women will experience obstetric complications during their pregnancies. The death of a woman during pregnancy and childbirth is not only a health issue but also a matter of social injustice . The main causes of maternal mortality are the Complications resulting from hemorrhage, anemia, unsafe abortions, eclampsia, sepsis & obstructed labour⁽²⁾.

Nurses have a vital role in preventing maternal mortality and morbidity due to obstetric related complications. The systematic review report reveals the following important educational interventions in improving the diagnosis and management of obstetric complications such as mobile applications, scenario-based training, station- based skill training, EMOC training program and short courses, simulation-based training, and skills and drills interventions⁽³⁾.The Competency Based Education is the way to promote the cognitive and psychomotor domain of learners significantly. This method will enhance the final year B.Sc nursing students to understand and train in certain clinical skill to manage some selected obstetric complications which will be the additional approach to enhance the students than usual education.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

STUDY SETTING AND DESIGN:

The study was conducted in the Kasturba Gandhi Nursing College at Puducherry and a quantitative research approach of Pre Experimental (One group pre and post-test) research designs was adopted for this study.

SAMPLE SIZE AND SAMPLING:

Participants were selected using a purposive sampling technique . The sample selected for the study was 80 Final year B.Sc Nursing students who fulfilled the inclusion criteria were selected for the study as samples. Inclusion criteria Final year B.Sc Nursing students, both male and female, available at the time of data collection, willing to participate in the study. Exclusion criteria include Repeater batch Students.

DATA COLLECTION TOOL:

The tool was developed based on review of literature, opinion from experts in the field of obstetric and gynecology. The tool consists of Three parts.

- Part A –Socio Demographic variables which includes age, gender, Previous knowledge regarding the topic.

- Part B– Structured Knowledge questionnaire regarding selected obstetric complications includes pregnancy induced hypertension and anemia. It consist of totally 40 multiple choice question 20 related to Pregnancy Induced Hypertension and 20 related question for Anemia. Each correct response was given score one whereas wrong response for score zero. Knowledge score converted into percentage.

Score interpretation:

- $\leq 50\%$ - Inadequate Knowledge
- 51-75% - Moderately adequate knowledge
- $>75\%$ - Adequate knowledge

- Part C – Observation checklist which includes measuring blood pressure, fetal heart rate monitoring and administration of injectable drugs including magnesium sulphate and iron sucrose. OSCE Checklist on Administration of Magnesium sulphate consists of 15 questions, Administration of Iron sucrose consists of 20 questions,

Monitoring Blood pressure consists of 20 questions, Monitoring Fetal Heart Rate consists of 10 questions. Skill score was converted into percentage.

Score interpretation:

- $\leq 50\%$ - Inadequate skill practice

- 51-75% - Moderately adequate skill practice

- $> 75\%$ - Adequate skill practice

RELIABILITY OF THE INSTRUMENT:

Reliability of research instrument is defined as the extent to which the instrument yields the same results on repeated measures. The reliability of the measuring instrument is a major criterion for assessing the quality and adequacy. The reliability of the tool was determined by calculating coefficient alpha (also called chronbach's alpha). The normal range of value for the reliability index is from 0.00 to +1.00. The higher the coefficient, more accurate the measure is in the present study. The reliability of the tool was done by using chronbach's alpha reliability formula. The chronbach's alpha score was $\alpha = 0.864$ for 40 items of Knowledge questionnaire and skill by checklist chronbach's alpha score was $\alpha = 0.758$ for 60 items.

PROCEDURE FOR DATA COLLECTION:

- ❖ The permission was obtained from IHEC and concerned authority to conduct a study.
- ❖ The permission was obtained from the Principal and the class coordinator from Kasturba Gandhi Nursing College.
- ❖ Period of data collection was six weeks.
- ❖ 80 final year B.Sc nursing students was selected by purposive sampling technique from Kasturba Gandhi Nursing College.

- ❖ The investigator was maintained good rapport with the students.
- ❖ Informed consent was obtained from the final year B.Sc Nursing Students.

PHASE I(PRE -TEST)

- ❖ Pretest was carried out for all 80 sample
- ❖ Demographic variables was collected , Knowledge questionnaire was distributed to all the students with proper instruction. 30 minutes was given to complete the knowledge questionnaire.
- ❖ Assessment of skill was done for all the samples using OSCE checklist. 20 minutes was be given for each sample to complete the skill.
- ❖ Four station (BP monitoring, Fetal Heart Rate monitoring, administration of injectable drugs includes MgSo4 and iron sucrose) was arranged to assess the skill by using the OSCE checklist.

PHASE II (INTERVENTION)

- ❖ Competency Based Education was given.
- ❖ Selected obstetric complication include Pregnancy induced hypertension and anemia was taught by using Power point presentation for 45 minutes.
- ❖ The investigator was demonstrated all four procedures in the assigned station for all 80 students (6 batches 15 students in each batch for 30 minutes).

PHASE III (POST-TEST)

- ❖ After 1 week the investigator was conducted the post test by using the same knowledge questionnaire and OSCE checklist.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

Data were analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics using SPSS version 21. The Mann-Whitney, paired t-test and p-value on comparison of pre and post-test knowledge and skill was carried out and the Wilcoxon signed ranks test was used to find the comparison within the groups. Chi square test was used to find out the association between variables in both the groups.

RESULTS

TABLE 1: Frequency and percentage distribution of the demographic variables of Final year B.Sc Nursing Students.

N = 80

Demographic variables		No. of Students	Percentage
AGE	19 to 20 Years	14	17.5%
	21 to 22 Years	65	81.3%
	More than 23 years	1	1.2%
GENDER	Male	22	27.5%
	Female	58	72.5%
PREVIOUS KNOWLEDGE REGARDING THE TOPIC	Yes	16	20.0%
	No	64	80.0%

Table 1 Shows the Frequency and percentage distribution of the demographic variables of Final year B.Sc Nursing Students

- With regards to age of Final year B.Sc Nursing Students, the highest number 65 (81.3%) belongs to the age group of 21 to 22 years, 14 (17.5%) were between 19 to 20 years, and one (1.2%) was more than 23 years of age.

- Regarding the gender two thirds of Students 58 (72.5%) were female and 22(27.5%) were male.
- In previous knowledge regarding the topic, out of 80 students 64(80%) were said no and 16 (20%) were said aware about the topic.

TABLE 2.1 : Distribution of level of knowledge on Anemia and Pregnancy Induced Hypertension among Final year B.Sc Nursing Students during pre test and post test.

Level of knowledge on selected obstetric complications		Pre-test		Post- test	
		N	%	N	%
Anemia	Inadequate knowledge	70	87.5%	0	0%
	Moderate knowledge	10	12.5%	8	10%
	Adequate knowledge	0	0%	72	90%
Pregnancy Induced Hypertension	Inadequate knowledge	68	85%	0	0%
	Moderate knowledge	12	15%	15	18.75%
	Adequate knowledge	0	0%	65	81.25%

In Assessment of knowledge on anemia ,out of 80 samples, most of them 70(87.5%) had inadequate knowledge, 10(12.5%) had moderate knowledge, and no one had adequate knowledge in pretest, and in the post test majority of them 72(90%) had adequate knowledge, eight (10%) had moderate knowledge, and no one had inadequate knowledge

In Assessment knowledge on Pregnancy Induced Hypertension ,Out of 80 samples, most of them 68(85%) had inadequate knowledge, 12(15%) had moderate knowledge, and no one had adequate knowledge in pretest and in the post test

knowledge most of them 65(81.25%) had adequate knowledge, 15(18.75%) had moderate knowledge, and no one had inadequate knowledge

It was inferred that after intervention the most of final year B.Sc Nursing Students had adequate knowledge in post test.

TABLE 2.2 : Distribution of skill on administration of MgSo4, Iron Sucrose, monitoring Blood Pressure and Fetal Heart Rate among Final year B.Sc Nursing Students during pre and post test

Level of skill on selected obstetric complications		Pre-test		Post- test	
		N	%	N	%
Administration of MgSo4	Inadequate skill	70	87.5%	0	0%
	Moderate skill	10	12.5%	8	10%
	Adequate skill	0	0%	72	90%
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Administration of Iron sucrose	Inadequate skill	68	85%	0	0%
	Moderate skill	12	15%	15	18.75%
	Adequate skill	0	0%	65	81.25%
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Monitoring Blood Pressure	Inadequate skill	62	77.5%	0	0%
	Moderate skill	18	22.5%	10	12.5%
	Adequate skill	0	0%	70	87.5%
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Monitoring FHR	Inadequate skill	71	88.75%	0	0%
	Moderate skill	9	11.25%	12	15%
	Adequate skill	0	0%	68	85%

In Assessment of skill by checklist on administration of MgSo₄, Out of 80 samples, most of them 70(87.5%) had inadequate skill , 10(12.5%) had moderate skill, and no one had adequate skill in pretest and in the post test most of them 72(90%) had adequate skill, 8(10%) had moderate skill, and no one had inadequate skill.

In Assessment of skill by checklist on administration of Iron sucrose, Out of 80 samples, most of them 68(85%) had inadequate skill , 12(15%) had moderate skill, and no one had adequate skill and in the post test most of them 65(81.25%) had adequate skill, 15(18.75%) had moderate skill, and no one had inadequate skill.

In Assessment of skill by checklist on monitoring Blood Pressure, Out of 80 samples, most of them 62(77.5%) had inadequate skill , 18(22.5%) had moderate skill, and no one had adequate skill and in the post test most of them 70(87.5%) had adequate skill, 10(12.5%) had moderate skill, and no one had inadequate skill.

In Assessment of skill by checklist on monitoring FHR, Out of 80 samples, most of them 71(88.75%) had inadequate skill , 9(11.25%) had moderate skill, and no one had adequate skill and in the post test most of them 68(85%) had adequate skill, 12(12%) had moderate skill, and no one had inadequate skill.

It was inferred that after intervention the most of final year B.Sc Nursing Students had adequate Skill in post test.

TABLE 3.1: Comparison of pre and post test level of Knowledge on Anemia and Pregnancy Induced Hypertension among Final year B.Sc Nursing Students .

knowledge		Mean	Standard Deviation	Standard Error mean	Paired t-Test	p-value
Anemia	Pre test	6.225	1.031	0.115	82.889	< .001
	Post test	18.113	0.656	0.073		
Pregnancy Induced Hypertension	Pre test	6.063	1.129	0.126	89.497	< .001
	Post test	17.738	0.545	0.061		

The pre test knowledge mean score on Anemia was 6.2 (SD =1.03) and the post test knowledge mean score was 18.1(SD = 0.65) .The obtained paired ‘t’ test value for knowledge on anemia was 82.889 and p value was highly significant at $p < 0.01$ level. Hence the stated hypothesis H1 was accepted. It was inferred that Competency Based Education on knowledge regarding selected obstetric complications among final year B.Sc Nursing students was effective

The pre test knowledge mean score on Pregnancy Induced Hypertension score was 6.06 (SD =1.12) and the post test knowledge mean score was 17.7 (SD = 0.54). The obtained paired ‘t’ test value for knowledge on Pregnancy Induced Hypertension was 89.467 and p value was highly significant $p < 0.01$ level. Hence the stated hypothesis H1 was accepted. It was inferred that Competency Based Education on knowledge regarding selected obstetric complications among final year B.Sc Nursing students was effective

TABLE 3.2: Comparison of pre and post test level of skill on administration of MgSo₄, Iron Sucrose, monitoring Blood Pressure and Fetal Heart Rate among final year B.Sc Nursing Students .

Skill		Mean	Standard Deviation	Standard Error mean	Paired t-Test	p-value
MgSo ₄	Pre test	4.475	0.503	0.056	81.993	< .001
	Post test	13.275	0.811	0.091		
Iron Sucrose	Pre test	5.838	0.892	0.1	85.618	< .001
	Post test	17.962	0.878	0.098		
Blood Pressure	Pre test	5.625	0.986	0.11	69.560	< .001
	Post test	17.325	1.077	0.12		
FHR	Pre test	3.175	0.689	0.077	63.145	< .001
	Post test	8.9	0.302	0.034		

- On Administration of MgSo₄ the pre test checklist mean score was 4.4(SD = 0.50) and the post test checklist mean score was 13.2(SD = 0.81) .The obtained paired ‘t’ value of checklist on MgSo₄ was 81.993 and p value was highly significant at p<0.01 level. Hence the stated hypothesis H₂ was accepted.
- On Administration of Iron sucrose the pre test checklist mean score was 5.8(SD = 0.89) and the post test mean score was 17.9 (SD =0.87). The obtained paired ‘t’ value of checklist on Iron sucrose was 85.618 and p value of was highly significant at p<0.01 level. Hence the stated hypothesis H₂ was accepted.
- On Monitoring Blood Pressure the pre test checklist mean score was 5.6 (SD =0.98) and the post test mean score was 17.3(SD = 1.07). The obtained paired ‘t’ value of checklist on blood pressure was 69.560 and p value was highly significant at p<0.01 level. Hence the stated hypothesis H₂ was accepted.
- On Monitoring FHR the pre test checklist mean score was 3.17(SD =0.68) and the post test checklist mean score was 8.9 (SD = 0.30). The obtained paired ‘t’ value

of checklist on FHR was 63.145 and p value was highly significant at $p < 0.01$ level. Hence the stated hypothesis H2 was accepted. It was inferred that Competency Based Education on Skill regarding selected obstetric complications among final year B.Sc Nursing students was effective

TABLE 4: Correlate the Knowledge & Skill regarding selected obstetric complications among final year B.Sc Nursing Students.

Test value		Anemia	Pregnancy Induced Hypertension	MgSo4	Iron Sucrose	Blood Pressure	FHR
Anemia	Pearson Correlation P-VALUE	1					
Pregnancy Induced Hypertension	Pearson Correlation P-VALUE	0.184 0.103	1				
MgSo4	Pearson Correlation P-VALUE	0.158 0.163	0.036 0.750	1			
Iron Sucrose	Pearson Correlation P-VALUE	-0.084 0.461	-0.002 0.983	-0.531 0.000	1		
Blood Pressure	Pearson Correlation P-VALUE	-0.028 0.805	-0.001 0.990	-0.403 0.000	0.750 0.000	1	
FHR	Pearson Correlation P-VALUE	0.015 0.894	0.116 0.306	0.232 0.038	0.047 0.680	0.359 0.001	1

TABLE 4: Indicates the Correlation level of the Knowledge & Skill regarding selected obstetric complications among final year B.Sc Nursing Students. Calculated correlation level between level of the Knowledge & Skill pretest was obtained by using Pearson Correlation P value . There is significant correlation between the level of knowledge and skill regarding selected obstetric complications among final year B.Sc Nursing Students.

Table 5: Association between the knowledge & skill regarding selected obstetric complications among final year B.Sc Nursing Students with selected demographic variables.

Demographic Variables		No.of students	ASSOCIATION BETWEEN THE KNOWLEDGE AND SKILL					MW / KW test	p-value
			Mean	Standard Deviation	Median	Percentile 25	Percentile 75		
AGE	19 to 20 years	14	5.43	1.02	5.5	5	6	6.5285	0.0382 (S)
	21 to 22 years	65	6.22	1.11	6	5	7		
	More than 23 years	1	5	.	5	5	5		
SEX	Male	22	5.91	0.97	6	5	7	1.7528	0.4163 (NS)
	Female	58	6.14	1.19	6	5	7		
PREVIOUS KNOWLEDGE ABOUT THE TOPIC	Yes	16	6.06	1	6	5	7	0.0155	0.9008 (NS)
	No	64	6.06	1.17	6	5	7		

Table 5 Despite the Association between the knowledge & skill regarding selected obstetric complications among final year B.Sc Nursing Students with selected demographic variables.

There is significant association between the level of knowledge & skill regarding selected obstetric complications among final year B.Sc nursing students with the demographic variable of age. There is no significant with other demographic variables .Hence, the stated hypothesis (H2) was accepted.

DISCUSSION

This chapter presents the major findings of the study and discusses them in relation to the similar studies conducted by other researchers. The main aim of the study was to evaluate the Effectiveness of Competency Based Education on Knowledge and Skill regarding selected Obstetric Complications among Final Year B.Sc Nursing Students in a selected Nursing College at Puducherry. Quantitative research approach was adopted for this study with Pre-experimental design of one group pre-test and post-test design. Population for this study consists of Final year B.Sc Nursing Students. The study was conducted at Kasturba Gandhi Nursing College, Puducherry. 80 Final year B.Sc nursing Students who fulfilling the inclusion criteria and are willing to participate in the study were selected by Purposive Sampling technique. Pre-test was conducted using structured knowledge questionnaire on selected obstetric complications includes Anemia and Pregnancy Induced Hypertension and Skill by using OSCE checklist include Administration of Magnesium Sulphate, Iron Sucrose, Monitoring Blood Pressure, Fetal Heart Rate by using OSCE Checklist. Competency Based Education was given Selected Obstetric Complications include Anemia and Pregnancy Induced Hypertension was taught by using Power point presentation for 45 minutes . The investigator was demonstrated all four procedures in the assigned station for all station for all 80 students (6 batches 15 students in each batch for 30 minutes). Post-test was conducted by using same Knowledge questionnaires and Skill by using OSCE Checklist after 1 weeks.

The response was analyzed through both descriptive statistics (Frequency and Percentage) and inferential statistics (Paired 't' test, Wilcoxon signed rank test and Mann–Whitney test). Discussion of the findings are presented based on the objectives of the study.

CONCLUSION:

The Statistical evidence proved that the Competency Based Education was effective in improving the Knowledge and Skill in selected obstetric complications among final year B.Sc Nursing Students while comparing the Pre -test and post-test. Hence the researcher concluded that the Competency Based Education can be effective in improving the Knowledge and skill regarding selected obstetric complications among final year B.Sc Nursing Students.

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